

Coupling numerical models of deltaic wetlands with AirSWOT, UAVSAR, and AVIRIS-NG remote sensing data – Supplementary Material –

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Outline. This document contains supplementary figures and table.

Figure S1. Comparison between AirSWOT derived water level and modelled water levels in the large scale Terrebonne model.

Figure S2. Comparison between AirSWOT derived water level and modelled water levels in the Atchafalaya model.

Figure S3. Comparison of measured and modelled water levels in 4 sites of the CRMS. In each subplot, the correspondent site is indicated in the lower right corner.

Figure S4. Comparison between measured and modelled water levels for all 13 CRMS used to validate the model.

Figure S5. Comparison between field measurements of SCC and modelled SCC.

Table S1. Longitude, Latitude, and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) for each CRMS site used to validate water levels calibrated with AirSWOT.

Site ID	Longitude	Latitude	RMSE (m)
302	-90.9170	29.1478	0.078
307	-90.8230	29.2511	0.080
322	-91.1045	29.2438	0.100
337	-90.3559	29.3092	0.078
338	-90.4182	29.3309	0.084
341	-90.5123	29.3091	0.080
345	-90.7613	29.1712	0.057
347	-90.6996	29.1640	0.075
374	-90.7930	29.1567	0.054
376	-90.8567	29.1277	0.062
377	-91.0108	29.2293	0.083
383	-90.9489	29.2075	0.069
421	-90.8244	29.1712	0.072
Overall	-	-	0.067